

for (*the requirements of*) worship, fifty garlands—*māla* 50— of such market flowers as are available at the particular season.

(20—23.) These above-mentioned gifts were made by the above-mentioned town, &c., from their property for as long a time as the moon, the sun and the earth exist. Nobody shall cause obstruction (*to the present owners*). For (*Vyāsa has said*): [*Here follow two of the usual minatory verses*].

XXI.—SIYADONI STONE INSCRIPTION.

BY PROFESSOR F. KIELHORN, Ph.D., C.I.E.; GÖTTINGEN.

In the *Journal, Beng. As. Soc.*, vol. XXXI, pp. 6-7, Dr. F. E. Hall had occasion to mention "a huge inscription," existing in some part of the State of Gwālior, a transcript of which, by a native, had been made over to him by Colonel (now General Sir) Alexander Cunningham. From the apparently very imperfect copy supplied to him, Dr. Hall was able to report that the inscription in the opening lines mentioned a king Mahendrapāla. Near where he is spoken of, was the date 960. Next came Bhoja, and then Mahendrapāla again, with the date 964. Further on Kshitipāla was mentioned; and, after him, Devapāla, the date 1005 being close by. These dates, according to Dr. Hall, were not sufficiently particularized for one to certify their era by calculation. Besides, the kings of the record were stated by Dr. Hall to have been memorialized as having granted land and other things, by way of local donaries, in ten several years, ranging from 960 to 1025. According to Sir A. Cunningham,¹ the actual site of the inscription was then unknown; and it has remained so for twenty-five years afterwards.²

In 1887, Dr. Burgess, when in the Lalitpur district of the North-Western Provinces, learnt that there was a large inscription at 'Siron Khurd,' about ten miles WNW. of the town of Lalitpur, Long. 78° 23' E., Lat. 24° 50' N. (*Indian Atlas*, quarter-sheet 70, NW.) And the inscription was found on the east of the village at which it had been reported to be,—and which in the inscription itself is called Siyaḍoṇī,—on the bank of the Kherār stream, in the precincts of a Jaina temple of Śāntinātha, where it had been recently set up by a Bania. It turned out to be the huge inscription mentioned by Dr. Hall; and I now edit it from impressions supplied to me by Dr. Burgess.

The inscription consists of forty-six lines; and the writing covers a space of about 5' 2½" broad by 3' 4" high. Of the first two and the last two lines large portions of the writing have either gone altogether or become illegible, by the flaking off of the edges of the stone; and from the same cause some *aksharas* have become illegible in lines 39-44. But the preservation of lines 3-38 is perfect almost throughout, so that here the actual reading of the stone hardly admits of any doubt whatever. The size of the letters is about ½". The characters are Nāgarī of about the eleventh century; down

¹ See *Journ., Beng. As. Soc.*, vol. XXXIII, p. 227.

² The inscription (or rather Dr. Hall's short account of it) has been referred to by Dr. Hörnle, in the *Centenary Review, Beng. As. Soc.*, part II, p. 208; and by Mr. Fleet, in the *Indian Antiquary*, vol. XV, p. 108, note 18, and vol. XVI, p. 178, who has pointed out the desirability of rediscovering and publishing the inscription.

to line 39, they are regularly and beautifully formed and skilfully engraved. The execution of lines 40-46 is somewhat inferior to the rest, and the difference in appearance is rendered more marked by the imperfect state of preservation of these concluding lines. The language of the inscription must be described as Sanskrit. Unless there was a date in any part of the concluding lines which is now illegible, the inscription itself is not dated; but it contains ten dates, some of which are historically important, while one is sufficiently particularized to ascertain from it the era employed, by calculation, as will be shown below.

The inscription consists of two parts. The first and by far the larger portion extends to about the middle of line 39; it is in prose, and records a large number of donations made at different times, from the (Vikrama) year 960 down to the (Vikrama) year 1025, and nearly every one of them by private individuals, in favour of various Brâhmanical deities, at Siyadonî. The second part, which is almost entirely in verse, comprises the remaining portion up to the end, and records the erection of a temple of Murâri (Vishnu).

THE FIRST PART.

To treat fully of the language of the first part, would require almost a separate treatise. The author or authors, though intending to write Sanskrit, had a very meagre knowledge of the grammar of that language; they were evidently influenced by, and have freely employed words, phrases, and constructions of, their vernacular.

As regards orthography, *b* has throughout been denoted by the sign for *v*; and the dental sibilant has often been employed for the palatal.³ The sign of the *jihvâmûlîya* occurs twenty-two times, almost exclusively in the phrases यक्ञित् and यक्ञोपि. The sign of the *upadhmanîya* has been correctly employed six times (*e.g.*, in •स्त्राभिःपर•, line 5, and •भित्तिःपश्चिमेन, line 13); but it has also been wrongly inserted three times (in •धूर्मटःपरि•, line 18, •ध्यातःपरम•, line 28, and •निष्कलःपरि•, line 29), and probably erroneously omitted twice (in •भित्तिः पश्चिमेन, line 25, and •रेभिः प्रदत्ता, line 35). Of individual words, the numeral त्रि has throughout been spelt तृ (in तृभाग, lines 24, 29, 30, and तृभुवन•, lines 25 and 27); संमार्जन throughout सम्मार्जन⁴ (*e.g.*, in lines 3, 6, 8, etc.); कालीन throughout कालिन (*e.g.*, in lines 3, 6, 20, etc.); and similarly we have भोगाधिना in line 38, for भोगाधीना. In line 8, we twice have अग्निन for आग्निन; throughout, frequently, अवासनिका, apparently for आवासनिका (*e.g.*, in lines 7, 8, etc.); and similarly a short vowel has been employed instead of a long one, and *vice versâ*, occasionally in other words. For षष्टि we have षष्ठी twice in line 17, and perhaps also in some of the compound numerals; for ताम्बूलिक (line 15), ताम्बोलिक in lines 25 and 26; for वैश्वानर, वैश्वान्दर in line 12. Through the influence of the vernacular, we have वणिक throughout for वणिज्; भीती in line 24 for भित्ति (lines 13 and 25); सिरिधर in line 39 for श्रीधर (line 37); कल्पपाल and कलपाल in lines 9 and 19, for कल्पपाल; etc.

The rules of *sandhi* have been persistently neglected; and as a specimen of an extraordinary *sandhi* I may point out •सुतारेभिः[,], for •सुता एभिः, *i.e.*, •सुताः एभिः, in line 35.

³ I consider it sufficient to state this and some of the following points once for all, and shall not consider it necessary to correct every error of this sort in the transcript of the text.

⁴ Compare the common सम्मान for संमान.

As regards the treatment of nouns in general, case-terminations have often been altogether omitted; sometimes wrong cases have been employed, masculine words treated as if they were neuter, and masculine or neuter forms of adjectives and pronouns used with reference to feminine nouns, etc. Thus, to give a few examples, instead of the well-known phrase परिपत्यनां करोति, we read fifteen times परिपत्यना करोति (*e.g.*, in lines 8, 9, 16, etc.); and similarly •विधारणा करोति, lines 13 and 20; परिपत्यनावाधा करोति, line 17; परिपत्यनाखत्रा करोति, lines 6 and 15; and खत्रावाधा ददाति, line 39. In line 3 we find प्रतिष्ठापित, qualifying नारायणभट्टारकस्य, which is separated from it by other inflected words; in line 4 वावण (for वावणो) गौदासुतः; in line 39 सिरिधर (for श्रीधरस्य) महादित्यसुतस्य; in line 16 अवलिप्त (for अवलिप्तौ) उवटकसहितौ.⁵ The words अधिकार, आघाट, पाद, भाग, हस्त are used as neuters in lines 34; 7, 12, 13, etc.; 6; 24, 29, 30; 26. In line 9 we have the Nominative स च स च for the Instrumental तेन तेन; in line 34 the Accusative •समेतां for the Nominative •समेता; in lines 32, 33, 38, 14, 22, अस्य and अमीषाम् for the feminine forms अस्याः and अमूषाम् or आसाम्. The final *visarga* of certain case-terminations has completely disappeared, *e.g.*, in •पातकै, lines 6, 15, 16, etc., and in •हेतो, lines 20, 25, 31.⁶

An extraordinary construction of the cardinal numerals, which I have already pointed out in other inscriptions, is illustrated by युगैकं, line 20, सहस्रैकं, line 28, पादैकं and द्रुमैकं, line 37, वीथीद्वौ, line 16, and गृहद्वौ 'two houses,' line 24. And, speaking of numerals, attention may be drawn here to the three different expressions पञ्चमहापातकै in line 6, महापञ्चपातकै in lines 15, 16, 18, and महापातकपञ्चकै or •कै: in lines 10, 27, 30; and to the strange संवत्सरसतेषु नवसत (*i.e.*, नवशत, for नवसु), meant to denote 'nine hundred years,' in lines 2, 5, 8, and 11.

The number of finite verbal forms employed is, as might have been expected in a record of the Middle Ages, small; and among them, I need point out only लिप्यति, used in a passive sense, in lines 6, 10, 15, etc. Among the verbal derivatives, there occur the wrong Gerunds लक्ष्य, line 6; उपर्जयित्वा, line 17, क्रयित्वा, line 25 (for क्रीत्वा, lines 9, 10, 19), एकमतीभूत्वा, lines 29, 30, and 33, and लिखाय्य, line 38; with the last of which may be compared the primary nouns पूजापन in lines 11 and 37, and मोक्षापन in line 38. And anomalously used is the Gerund मिलित्वा in the phrase समस्तलोकानां मिलित्वा in line 26, apparently meaning 'before all the people assembled.'

Of frequent occurrence is सत्क, which thirteen times may be considered a secondary suffix conveying a possessive sense or expressing the meaning of a Genitive case; *e.g.*, in सीयडोणिसत्कमण्डपिकायां, line 6, वामनसत्कवीथी, line 12, चाण्डसत्कावासनिका, line 32, and विग्रहपालसत्कद्रुम, line 9 (= विग्रहपालीयद्रुम, line 24); while twice it is, exceptionally, like an independent word, construed with a preceding Genitive, in यस्य यस्य सत्कमण्डभाण्डं, line 9, and समस्तकक्षपालानां सत्कहृद्वानामुपरि, line 19.

Under the head of compounds, I may point out the violation of an elementary rule of grammar, in महद्वर्गहेतोः, line 8, महद्वर्गार्थहेतो, line 20, महन्तधर्मार्थहेतो or •हेतो: in lines 25 and 28, and महन्तधर्मार्थहेतो or •हेतो: in lines 11, 29, 31, and 33; the use of phrases like दिनं प्रति, line 6, for प्रतिदिनं (actually used in lines 6, 10, and 28), and मासाश्चासं, line 20, or मासाश्चासं प्रति, lines 29 and 37, instead of प्रतिमासं (line 45); and the employment of the Nominative cases in passages such as सूत्रधारजेजपस्तथा विसिञ्जाकस्तथा भलुषाकस्तथा

⁵ *I.e.*, one case-termination suffices for several nouns, as it already does, occasionally, in the R̥gveda.

⁶ In केशिञ्जावाह षष्ठरावाह, line 4, we seem to have Apabrahm̃sa Nominative cases; see *Ind. Ant.*, vol. XVI, p. 207.

जीगूकद्रकादीनां, line 29 (and similarly in lines 7, 19, 20, 27, and 31), where, in proper Sanskrit, the formation of a Dvandva compound would have been resorted to.

Moreover, the first part of the inscription contains a considerable number of words which either do not occur in Sanskrit literature at all, or for which the dictionary furnishes no appropriate meaning; and some of which undoubtedly were taken from the vernacular. These words I give in the following alphabetical list, in which I also include some words which appear to be proper names of places or localities, but about the actual meaning of which I cannot be certain : —

अक्षयनीमी in line 6, and अक्षयनीमिका in lines 7, 9, 21, etc., = अक्षयनीवि 'a perpetual endowment.'

अपसरक in अपसरकसहित in lines 7, 17, 24, and अपसरकप्राङ्गणसहित, lines 32 and 33, said of houses, etc.; compare the Hindi ओसरा 'a porch, portico, peristyle, vestibule,' Marāṭhī ओसरी.

अवासनिका in lines 7, 8, etc., apparently for आवासनिका, derived from आवास 'a dwelling, residence.'

आहाड in समस्तआहाडसम्बद्धसिलाकूटानां in line 30; perhaps a place where stone-cutters work, a quarry (?).

उवटक in line 25, and in उवटकसहित, lines 12, 13, 16, etc., said of houses, etc.; compare the Marāṭhī ओटा 'the little wall or raised edge which runs along the brink of the raised mass on which the house stands,' and ओटी, 'a veranda, porch, vestibule.'

कांसारक in कांसारकवीथी, line 15; compare the Hindi कसार and the Marāṭhī कांसार or कासार 'a brazier,' (कांस्यकार).

कंदासघूट in line 15.

कन्दुक three times in line 10; compare the Hindi कान्दू 'a certain tribe whose occupation it is to fry corn, prepare sweetmeats, etc., a sugar-boiler.'

कृतोपसन्ना, qualifying वीथी, in lines 27, 35, and 38.

कौमिक in line 2; and in lines 19 and 30, both times compounded with a proper name; denoting perhaps an office.

खश्ना in परिपन्थनाखश्ना, lines 6, 10, 15, and खश्नावाधा, line 39; compare the Hindi खसर 'damages, loss, injury, fraud.'

ग्रहपतिक in line 15, probably for गृहपति.

घ्राणक in line 28, and घ्राणक in line 31; compare the Marāṭhī घाणा 'an oil-mill.'

चूंआ or चूंआं, in चूंआंवीथी and चूंआवीथी, lines 13 and 14.

छाया in स्वकीयस्वकीयच्छाया, lines 7 and 33.

छेण्डिका in lines 8, 21, and 24.

जगति in line 35, for जगती, probably a kind of building; see *Indian Antiquary*, vol. XIV, p. 161, note 27.

ताली in line 9, and तालि in line 20, perhaps a particular measure of spirituous liquor.

तिखरा in तिखरावीथी, line 35.

हारोष्ठ in स्वकीयावासनिकाहारोष्ठ, line 14, हारोष्ठनिष्कासप्रवेसक, line 32, and निष्कासप्रवेसहारोष्ठकं, line 33; compare हारकोष्ठक 'a gate-chamber,' in the Index of the *Divyāvadāna*.

नेमक in नेमकवणिक, lines 5, 11, 16, etc., and नेमकजातिवणिक, line 37; perhaps equivalent to the Hindi and Marāṭhī निमक 'salt.'

पञ्चकुल in lines 2, 18, 29, 30, 36; an office, apparently similar to the Marāṭhī पंच or पंचार्हत. Compare *Ind. Ant.*, vol. XI, p. 221, l. 21, and p. 242, l. 9; also vol. XII, p. 195, note.

पञ्चिक in कल्लपालमहत्तकपञ्चिकः, line 19.

पालिका in line 26, and पलिका in lines 28 and 31; probably = पालि=प्रख.

प्रसन्नदेवियारक in line 12.

भरण in भरणं भरणं प्रति, line 30; perhaps 'a load' (of stores).

मण्डपिका in lines 6, 19, 29, 30, 45; evidently some public or official building of the town. Compare *Ind. Ant.*, vol. XIV, p. 10, second col., line 5; and *Journ. Beng. As. Soc.*, vol. XXX, p. 332, last line.

महर in ताम्बोलिकमहर, line 26; compare महत्तक in कल्लपालमहत्तक, line 19; and the Hindi महर 'a chief.' Compare Dr. Hultzsch, *ante*, p. 161, note 24.

सुद्रयित्वा in line 6.

मुलादतण in line 11.

युग or युगा in युगैका देया, line 6, युगैकं युगैकं प्रति, line 20, and समस्तयुगानामुपरि, line 21. रसीके in line 24.

वंसोपक in line 10, and विसोवक in line 26; perhaps 'the twentieth part of' or a name of a particular coin. We may compare विसोपका, which several times occurs in a copperplate inscription of the Lucknow Museum.

धारणा in lines 13 and 20; equivalent to परिपत्यना or विघ्न.

वषयण in line 33, compounded with a proper name, and denoting perhaps a trade.

सिलाकूट in line 30, = शिलाकुट्ट in verse 101 of the Sāsbaḥū inscription, *Ind. Ant.*, vol. XV, p. 40, 'a stone-cutter.'

खोलीपात or खोलिकापात in lines 12, 16, 21, 23, etc., and in अवासनिकाखोलीपात and अवासनिकाखोलिकापात in lines 13, 22, and 8; and ओलीपात in lines 35 and 38.

हट्ट 'a market' in चतुर्हट्ट, line 15, चतुष्कहट्ट, line 35, दोसिहट्ट, lines 12, 16, 20, 21, 29, प्रसन्नहट्ट, line 13, and महत्तकहट्ट, lines 45 and 46; (also in हट्टरथ्या, lines 12, 14, etc.)

As regards the contents, the first part of the inscription is divided, by means of ornamental full-stops, into twenty-seven sections; and it records as many donations, made at different times, and almost all of them by traders and artizans, for providing the usual materials of worship of Vishṇu and other deities, at the town of Sīyadoṇī. The inscription, in fact, is a collective public copy of a series of deeds; and the occasional remarks that a certain portion was written by the *karanika*, or writer of legal documents, Sarvahari, the son of Bhochuka (line 4), another by Rachchhāka, the son of Sarvahari (line 34), another by Svāmikumāra, another son of Sarvahari (line 36), and another again by the *karanika* Dhīravarman, the son of Svāmikumāra (line 39), were copied with the rest from the original deeds, and must not be taken to refer to the inscription itself. There are some, I believe, minor points in several of the deeds here presented to us, which, owing at least in part to the ungrammatical state of the language and to the employment of obscure expressions, I do not fully understand. But the general import of the various donations is clear enough, and may be seen from the following statement, from which I omit, as of no interest, all reference to the boundaries of buildings which in the original are given with scrupulous care. Any

remarks of historical importance or of more general interest, which may be incidentally furnished by these deeds,—considering the great length of the inscription, they are disappointingly few,—will be treated of below.

Abstract of the contents of the first part of the inscription (lines 1—39).

1. [Lines 1—4]: Samvat 960, Śrāvāṇa (in words and figures). The whole town gave a field measuring 200 by 225 *hastas* to Śrī-Nārāyaṇa-bhaṭṭāraka, set up by the merchant Chaṇḍuka, the son of Saṅgaṭa, in the southern part of the town.

2. [4—7]: Samvat 964, Mārgaśira va.di. 3 (in words and figures). The *Mahā-sāmāntādhipati* Undabhaṭa assigned an endowment, securing the daily payment of a quarter of a *pañchīyakadrumma* and of one *yugā* (?) to Śrī-Vishṇu-bhaṭṭāraka, set up by Chaṇḍuka.

3. [7—8]: The same date. The merchants Chaṇḍuka, Sāvasa, and Māhapa, sons of Saṅgaṭa, gave an *avāsānikā* (or residence) comprising four houses to Śrī-Vishṇu-bhaṭṭāraka, set up by Chaṇḍuka, the son of Saṅgaṭa.

4. [8—10]: Samvat 965, Āśvina śu.di. 1 (in words and figures). The merchant Nāgāka, son of Chāṇḍū, made an endowment acquired of certain potters, to the effect that the distillers of spirituous liquor, on every cask of liquor, were to give liquor worth half a *vīgrahapāladrumma* (?) to the god (Vishṇu).

5. [10]: The merchant Nāgāka, son of Chāṇḍū, assigned (an endowment securing) the daily payment by certain sugar-boilers of a *varāhakayavimsopaka* (?).

6. [11—13]: Samvat 967, Phālguna va.di. 15 (in words and figures). The merchant Vāsudeva gave (an *avāsānikā* ?) in the Dosihaṭṭa to Śrī-Vishṇu-bhaṭṭāraka, set up by Vāsudeva near (?) the Śrī-Vishṇu-bhaṭṭāraka set up by Chāṇḍuka; and a house of his own, to the (same) god, (for the worship of the sacred fire).

7. [13—15]: The merchant Chāṇḍuka gave a *vīthī* (or shop) in the Prasanahaṭṭa; and the same Chāṇḍuka, son of Saṅgaṭa, gave four hereditary *vīthīs* of his own to Śrī-Vishṇu-bhaṭṭāraka.

8. [15—16]: The seller of betel Keśava, son of Vaṭeśvara, gave a hereditary *vīthī* of his own in the Chaturhaṭṭa to Śrī-Vishṇu-bhaṭṭāraka, set up by Chāṇḍū.

9. [16—17]: The merchant Nāgāka, son of Chāṇḍū, gave two *vīthīs*, acquired in the Dosihaṭṭa, to Śrī-Vishṇu-bhaṭṭāraka.

10. [17—18]: The merchant Śilūka, son of Mahapā, gave a *vīthī* acquired by him to Śrī-Nārāyaṇa-bhaṭṭāraka.

11. [18—20]: Samvat 969, Māgha śu.di. 5 (in words and figures). The merchant Nāgāka, son of Chāṇḍū, gave a capital of 1,350 *śrīmadādivarāhadrammas*, invested with the distillers of spirituous liquor, who were to pay every month half a *vīgrahatungīyadrumma* on every cask of liquor (?) to Śrī-Vishṇu-bhaṭṭāraka.

12. [20—21]: The merchant Nāgāka, son of Chāṇḍū, gave an endowment realizing a payment of two *kapardakas* on certain *yugās* in the Dosihaṭṭa (?).

13. [21—22]: Nāgāka gave a *vīthī* acquired in the Dosihaṭṭa to Śrī-Nārāyaṇa-bhaṭṭāraka..

14. [22—23]: Nāgāka, son of Chāṇḍū, gave three *vīthīs* of his own to Śrī-Nārāyaṇa-bhaṭṭāraka.

15. [23—24]: The merchant Bhâila, son of Govinda, gave a hereditary *vîthî* (realizing one-third of a *vigrahapâliyadramma* ?) to Śrî-Vâmanasvâmidêva.

16. [24—25]: Nâgâka gave two houses to Tribhuvanasvâmidêva.

17. [25—26]: The seller of betel Dhamâka gave an *uvaṭaka* bought by him to Śrî-Umâmaheśvara.

18. [26—27]: Samvat 994, Vaiśâkha va.di. 5 samkrântau. The sellers of betel, Savara, son of Keśava, and Mâdhava, son of Ichchû, gave an endowment realizing the payment of a *vigrahadrammavisovaka* on every *pâlikâ* of leaves to the god (Vishṇu), set up by Chaṇḍûka.

19. [27]: Sâvasa gave a *vîthî* to Tribhuvanasvâmidêva.

20. [27—28]: Nâgâka gave a *palikâ* of oil from every oil-mill of the oil-makers (?).

21. [28—29]: Samvat 1005, Mâgha śu.di. 5 (*in words and figures*). The Mahâjans in the Dosihatṭa assigned a monthly payment of one-third of a *dramma* to Śrî-Bhâilasvâmidêva, set up by the merchant Vikrama.

22. [29—30]: The Sûtradhâra Jcjava, Visiâka, Bhaluâka, and other stonecutters, assigned a payment of one-third of a *vigrahapâladramma* on every *bharana* to Śrî-Vishṇu-bhaṭṭâraka.

23. [30—31]: Samvat 1008, Mâgha śu.di. 11 (*in figures, only*). Keśava, Durgâditya, and other oil-makers, gave a *palikâ* of oil from every oil-mill to Śrî-Chakrasvâmidêva, set up by Purandara in the temple of Vishṇu erected by Chaṇḍû.

24. [31—33]: The merchants Mahâditya and Nohala, sons of Pappâ, gave an *avâsanikâ*, comprising three houses, to Śrî-Chakrasvâmidêva, set up by Pappâka, the son of Dedaḍâ.

25. [33—34]: Samvat 991, Mâgha śu.di. 10 (*in figures*). Nâgâka, son of Châṇḍû, Dedaika, Vâli, and Rudâka, sons of Jâjû, and Chhitarâka, son of Sâvâ, gave an *avâsanikâ* with the houses and *vîthîs* belonging to it to the god (Vishṇu).

26. [34—36]: Dedaika, Vâlîka and Rudâka, sons of Jâjû, gave a *vîthî* in the Chatushkahatṭa to Śrî-Vishṇu-bhaṭṭâraka, set up by Chaṇḍû.

27. [36—39]: Samvat 1025, Mâgha va.di. 9 (*in figures*). The merchant Śrîdhara, son of Mahâditya, assigned a quarter of a *śrîmadâdivarâhadramma*, paid as the rent of a *vîthî* (?) to Śrî-Vishṇu-bhaṭṭâraka, set up by Mahâditya in the temple of Vishṇu erected by Châṇḍu.

From the above abstract it will appear that most of the donations recorded here were made in favour of the god Vishṇu, under the names of Vishṇu-bhaṭṭâraka, Nârâyana-bhaṭṭâraka, Vâmanasvâmidêva, and Chakrasvâmidêva. The same divinity I understand to be denoted by the name Tribhuvanasvâmidêva. But besides him, we find among the donees also Umâmaheśvara, clearly a form of the god Śiva, and Bhâilasvâmidêva, a name which in a fragmentary inscription from Bhilsa, mentioned by Dr. Hall in the *Journ. Beng. As. Soc.*, vol. XXXI, p. 112, is distinctly given as a designation of Ravi, 'the Sun.'

In connection with the objects of donation, attention may be drawn to the various names of coins mentioned in the inscription, which are as follows: *Dramma*, line 29;

⁷ Compare also *Ind. Ant.*, vol. XVI, p. 202.—Vishṇu bears the name *Vâllabhâṭṭaravâmin* in the Gwâlior inscription, edited by Dr. Hultzsch, *ante*, p. 154.—In the present inscription, I would draw attention to the name *Śrî-A[mba]lohîdevî*, which occurs in line 35, and which may denote a divinity. [Possibly the god Bhâilasvâmin was named after the merchant Bhâila (line 23), who might have been the father of the merchant Vikrama (line 29), who founded the temple.—E. H.]

Pañchiyaka-dramma, lines 6 and 37; *Vigrahapāla-dramma*, line 30; *Vigrahapālīya-dramma*, line 24; *Vigrahapālasatka-dramma*, line 9; and *Vigrahatuṅgiya-dramma*, line 20; *Śrīmadādivarāha*, line 19, and *Śrīmadādivarāha-dramma*, line 37; *Varāhakaya-vimsopaka* (?), line 10, and *Vigraha-dramma-visovaka*, line 26; and *Kapardaka*, line 20; to which may be added here at once, from the second part of the inscription, *Kākinī* and *Varātakā*, in line 45.

Among the donors, the only personage of importance is Undabhāṭa, who is described here (in line 5) as *mahāprātihāra*, *samadhigatāśeshamahāśabda*, and *Mahāsāmantādhipati*, and who clearly is the *Mahāsāmantādhipati* Undabhāṭa, mentioned, with the date 960, in two short inscriptions at Terahi, a village about twenty-seven miles NW. of Siyaḍonī. I have shown elsewhere⁸ that the date of the Terahi inscriptions must be referred to the Vikrama era, and this alone would prove that the date assigned to Undabhāṭa's donation in the present inscription, the year 964, and together with it all the other dates, are recorded in the same era. But even irrespectively of the Terahi inscriptions, the date of the donation No. 18, in which the 5th of the dark half of the month Vaiśākha of the year 994 is coupled with a *samkrānti* or entrance of the sun into a sign of the zodiac, contains sufficient *data* to enable us to prove that the era which we are here concerned with is the Vikrama era, that the years mentioned are southern Vikrama years, and that the arrangement of the lunar fortnights followed was the *amānta* or southern arrangement. For, taking the figures 994 to denote the southern Vikrama year 994 expired, the 5th of the dark half of Vaiśākha, by the *amānta* scheme of the lunar fortnights, corresponds to Sunday, 22nd April, A.D. 938, when the 5th *tithi* of the dark half ended about 17h. 45m. after mean sunrise, and when, about 14h. 6m. after mean sunrise, the sun *did* enter into the zodiacal sign of Vṛisha, exactly as required by the details of the date.⁹ Accordingly, the donations spoken of in the inscription were made between A.D. 903-4 and 968-9.

From the introductory remarks to the donations Nos. 11, 21, 23, and 27 (lines 18, 29, 30, and 36) we learn that the town of Siyaḍonī, in the year 969 = A.D. 912-13, was held by (or, as the inscription expresses it, was in the enjoyment of) the *Mahārājādhirāja*, the illustrious Dhūrbhāṭa; and in the years 1005 = A.D. 948-49, 1008 = A.D. 951-52, and 1025 = A.D. 968-69, by the *Mahārājādhirāja* Nishkalaṅka. A third personage, described, so far as one can see, as *samadhigatāśeshamahāśabda* and *Mahāsāmantādhipati*, who appears to have held a position similar to that of Dhūrbhāṭa and Nishkalaṅka, was mentioned, with the date 960 = A.D. 903-4, in line 2, but his name is

⁸ *Ind. Ant.*, vol. XVII, p. 201.

⁹ The possible equivalents for Vaiśākha va. di. 5 would be—

- (1) for the Northern Vikrama year 994 current—
 - a. by the *pūrṇimānta* scheme, Wednesday, 16th March, A.D. 936;
 - b. by the *amānta* scheme, Thursday, 14th April, A.D. 936;
 and *samkrāntis* took place on 22nd March and 22nd April;
- (2) for the Northern Vikrama year 994 expired, or the southern current year—
 - a. by the *pūrṇimānta* scheme, Tuesday, 4th April, A.D. 937;
 - b. by the *amānta* scheme, Wednesday, 3rd May, A.D. 937;
 and *samkrāntis* took place on 22nd April and 23rd May;
- (3) for the Southern Vikrama year 994 expired—
 - a. by the *pūrṇimānta* scheme, Saturday, 24th March, A.D. 938;
 - b. by the *amānta* scheme, Sunday, 22nd April, A.D. 938;
 and *samkrāntis* took place on 22nd March and 22nd April.

bhaya or Nirbhayanarendra, and that Rājasekhara in some passages of his plays now illegible. Under these nobles, the affairs of the town would seem to have been managed by an assembly of five called *pañchakula*, and by a committee of two, appointed from time to time by the town. The *Mahārājādhirājas* themselves were subordinate to, and derived their authority from, the paramount lords of the country, of whom the inscription mentions:—

In line 1, with the date 960=A.D. 903-4, the [*Paramabhaṭṭāraka*] *Mahārājādhirāja*, and *Parameśvara*, the illustrious Mahendrapāladeva¹⁰ [meditating, in all probability, on the feet of the *Paramabhaṭṭāraka*, *Mahārājādhirāja*, and *Parameśvara*, the illustrious Bhojadeva];

In line 4, with the date 964=A.D. 907-8, again, the same *P. M.* and *P.* the illustrious Mahendrapāladeva, meditating on the feet of the *P. M.* and *P.* the illustrious Bhojadeva; and

In line 28, with the date 1005=A.D. 948-49, the *P. M.* and *P.* the illustrious Devapāla, meditating on the feet of the *P. M.* and *P.* the illustrious Kshitipāladeva.

We are nowhere in the inscription distinctly told what was the name of the country over which these particular sovereigns held sway, or of their capital; but as the inscription, in line 40, speaks of a ruler of Mahodayā who granted a town to certain Brāhman descendants of whom lived at Sīyaḍonī, we shall not be wrong in assuming that Bhojadeva, Mahendrapāladeva, Kshitipāladeva and Devapāla were kings of Mahodayā, better known as Kanyakubjā (or Kanauj).

The main importance of our inscription then lies in this, that it furnishes, together with certain dates, the names of two pairs of kings of Kanyakubjā,—

Bhoja; succeeded by

Mahendrapāla, who was ruling in A.D. 903-4 and 907-8; and

Kshitipāla; succeeded by

Devapāla, who was ruling in A.D. 948-49.

Of these, I do not hesitate to identify Bhoja with the Bhojadeva of the Deogaḍh, Gwālior, and Peheva inscriptions¹¹ of A.D. 862, 876, and 882.

As regards Kshitipāla, there is nothing in our inscription to show that he was the *immediate* successor of Mahendrapāla; but I shall try to prove that such *was* the case and that Kshitipāla, in fact, was the son of Mahendrapāla.

In an article on the date of the poet Rājasekhara,¹² Mr. Fleet has put together certain facts concerning that poet which had been already drawn attention to by Professor Pischel,¹³ and which amount to this, that one or more of the poet's plays were acted, at Mahodayā or Kanyakubjā, before a king Mahīpāla, a son of a king Nir-

¹⁰ In the original, the first syllable is illegible, but there cannot be the slightest doubt about the correctness of the above name; nor is it, in my opinion, at all doubtful that the name of the sovereign on whose feet Mahendrapāla was meditating, was Bhojadeva. And these two sovereigns are clearly the same Bhojadeva and Mahendrapāla who are mentioned in the second deed, in line 4; so that the inscription speaks of only *one* Bhojadeva, and of only *one* Mahendrapāladeva.

¹¹ See *Archæol. Survey of India*, vol. X, p. 101; Dr. Hultzsch, *ante*, p. 155; and Mr. Fleet in *Ind. Ant.*, vol. XV, p. 109. I may draw attention here to the somewhat unusual phrase *mahī-pravardhamāna-kalyāṇa-vijayarājye*, which the Sīyaḍonī inscription has in common with, at any rate, the Deogaḍh inscription, and with the Asnī inscription which will be mentioned below.

¹² See *Ind. Ant.*, vol. XVI, pp. 175-178.

¹³ See *Göttingische Gelehrte Anzeigen*, 1883, p. 1221.

describes himself as the *guru* or *upādhyāya* of this same Nirbhaya, while elsewhere he either calls himself the *guru* of Mahendrapāla, or describes Mahendrapāla as his *śishya*. Mr. Fleet passes over Professor Aufrecht's identification of Nirbhaya with Mahendrapāla,¹⁴ the correctness of which would appear to be almost self-evident; but in identifying the poet's Mahīpāla with the king Mahīpāla of the Asnī inscription¹⁵ of the (Vikrama) year 974, he has been the first to *prove* that Rājasekhara lived in the beginning of the tenth century A.D. What was wanted to remove all possible doubt as to the correctness of Mr. Fleet's identification, was an epigraphical record in which Mahīpāla is connected with Mahodayā, and which furnishes the name of Mahīpāla's father, Mahendrapāla; and this want is supplied, I believe, by the present inscription, the probable importance of which Mr. Fleet has not failed to notice.

The names Mahīpāla and Kshitipāla being synonymous, I now identify the Kshitipāla of the present inscription with the Mahīpāla of the Asnī inscription, whom from that very inscription we know to have ruled in A.D. 917-18; and I consider our Mahendrapāla, for whom we have the dates A.D. 903-4 and 907-8, to be Rājasekhara's Mahendrapāla, *alias* Nirbhayanarendra, the father of Mahīpāla (our Kshitipāla). I also, of course, accept Mr. Fleet's statement that the Mahishapāla,¹⁶ who in the Asnī inscription is described as the predecessor of Mahīpāla, must be identical with Nirbhayanarendra (or, I may add, Mahendrapāla); and I am, I believe, able to show that Kshitipāla or Mahīpāla,—just as his father had three names,—in all probability also was known by a third name which is preserved to us in the Khājurāho inscription of the Chandella Yaśovarman of the (Vikrama) year 1011, = A.D. 954-55. From that inscription we learn that Yaśovarman (*alias* Lakshavarman) had received a certain image of Vaikuṅṭha from Devapāla, who must have been a well-known royal personage, the son of Herambapāla, the image having previously been received by Herambapāla from Sāhi, the king of Kīra. The reign of Yaśovarman having closed (probably shortly) before A.D. 954, the Devapāla spoken of in his inscription can be no other than our Devapāla of Mahodayā, for whom we have the date A.D. 948-49, and his father Herambapāla therefore in all likelihood is no other than Kshitipāla, *alias* Mahīpāla.

To sum up, the names of the four sovereigns of Mahodayā or Kanyakubjā, presented to us in our inscription, together with their known dates, would be as follows:—

- (1) Bhoja, A.D. 862, 876, and 882.
- (2) Mahendrapāla, or Nirbhayanarendra, or Mahishapāla, A.D. 903 and 907; pupil of the poet Rājasekhara.
- (3) His son Kshitipāla, or Mahīpāla, or Herambapāla, A.D. 917; patron of Rājasekhara; contemporaneous with Sāhi, the king of Kīra, and (as I have tried to show *ante*, p. 121), with the Chandella Harshadeva, the father of Yaśovarman.

¹⁴ See *Göttingische Gelehrte Anzeigen*, 1883, p. 1221.

¹⁵ First edited by Mr. Fleet in *Ind. Ant.*, vol. XVI, pp. 173-175.

¹⁶ I give this name on Mr. Fleet's authority. The published photolithograph would rather have induced me to conjecture Mahindrāpāla (probably for Mahīndrapāla, if not actually Mahendrapāla).

- (4) His son Devapâla, A.D. 948; contemporaneous with the Chandella Yaśovarman (*alias* Lakshavarman). Whether Devapâla is identical with Vijayapâla, who in an inscription from Alwâr, of the Vikrama year 1016=A.D. 959-60, is described as the successor of Kshitipâla, I am unable to determine (see *Proceedings, As. Soc. Beng.*, 1879, p. 162).

I abstain for the present from any speculations on the possible predecessors or successors of these kings, but, in conclusion, I must point out that our Devapâla can have nothing to do with the Devapâla in Dr. Hörnle's list in the *Centenary Review, Beng. As. Soc.*, part II, p. 208, or in the lists of Sir A. Cunningham in *Archæological Survey of India*, vol. XV, p. 149, and elsewhere.

THE SECOND PART.

On the second part of the inscription (lines 39-46), which, as I have stated above, is almost entirely in verse, I need only add a few words here. The language here, too, is Sanskrit, and it is generally more correct than in the preceding portion, but by no means free from mistakes. Thus, we find in line 42 the Ablative हिरण्यजीवात्, used instead of the Genitive; in line 43 प्रविवेस (for प्रविवेश) used in a causal sense; in line 42 the barbarous कारापयामास; in line 39, for the sake of the metre, वमथु for वमथु; in line 42 the crude form आवाण for आवन्; in lines 39 and 40 offences against the metre; etc.

As regards the contents, after the words 'om, om, adoration to Gaṇapati,' and two verses invoking the blessings of Gaṇanâtha and Trivikrama (Vishṇu), we are told that a certain prince at Mahodayâ, which is compared with Indra's town Amarâvatî, once gave the town Râyakka to some Brâhmanas, who after it were called Râyakkabhaṭṭas. One of their descendants, named Vaśishṭha, happened to come on matters of business 'here', to Sîyaḍonî, where he dwelt near the Râja of the place whose name apparently was Harirâja. And Vaśishṭha's son, Dâmodara, founded here a temple of Murâri (Vishṇu), furnished it with an image of the god, provided it with a garden, and probably endowed it with funds for the worship of the deity. The concluding line would appear to say that the father of Dâmodara died in battle.

[This temple of Vishṇu has since been identified by Dr. A. Führer with a large ruined shrine at the neighbouring village of Satgatto, to the NE. of Siron. Near the ruined temple is a large *baoli* or well, still in fair preservation, and the village abounds in fine statues of Vishṇu,—some of which have been transferred to the Lucknow Museum.—J. B.]

I have stated before that the concluding lines of the inscription are more or less damaged, and there are some passages in them which, in consequence, I fail to understand properly; but the above gives correctly the general sense of the original, and I have omitted nothing which would be of any importance to the historian.

The town Râyakka, mentioned in the above, I am unable to identify. With the term Râyakkabhaṭṭa we may compare Râyakavâla, the designation of a Brâhman caste, in line 27 of the inscription of Bhîmadeva II. published in *Ind. Ant.*, vol. XI, p. 71.

TEXT.¹⁷

1. श्री¹⁸ श्री नमो भग[व]ते वासुदेवाय¹⁹ [य?]²⁰
धिरा[ज?] — — —²¹ [देवपा?]²² हाराजाधिराजपरमेश्वर[श्री]—[हेन्द्र]पालदेव-
पादा[नां]²³ म[हीप्र] -

2. वर्धमानकल्याणविजय — [ज्ये?][सं] — — [रस]तेषु²⁴ नवसत षड्यधिकेषु आव
.²⁵ सम्बत् ९६० आव[ण].²⁶ गताशेषमहा[श]ब्दम[हा]सामन्ताधिपति[श्रीमदु]—[न्द्र?]
.²⁷ [भु]ज्यमानस्त[त्पादाधिष्ठित][व?]²⁸ [कु?]²⁹ [कौ]प्तिके श्रीपञ्च[स्था?]
.³⁰ [क?] द्वाविंसतिकच्छितराकयोर्वारि [सतीदृसे] का[ले वर्त्तमाने वार?] प्रमु[ख?] -

3. सकलस्थानेन संसारस्थानित्यत्वं बुद्ध्या³¹ पुण्ययशोभिहृद्ये स्वकीयतलसीमाप्रतिव[क्षेत्रं?]
[पूर्वपश्चि]मतो हस्तद्विसतमात्रं दक्षिणोत्तरतो वा सपादहस्तद्विसत[मात्र]श्च वणिकचण्डुकेन³² सङ्गटसुतेन
प्रतिष्ठापित³³ पत्तनस्य दक्षिणदिग्दिग्भागे पश्चिमाभिमुखश्रीनारायणभट्टारकस्याव[लेपनस]म्मा[र्जना]ङ्ग-
[राग]धूपप्रदीपनैवेद्याद्यर्थं निवेदितं धर्माय मत्वा आचन्द्रार्कक्षित्युदधिसमकालिनं यावन्न कैश्चि[त्परिप-
न्यना कर्त्त?][व्या] इ[ति]

4. सकलस्थानानुमतेन वा[र]स्वहस्तायेति ॥ छ ॥ मतं केसिआवारु च्छितरावारु साक्षिणौ
श्रुते³⁴ लिखितसाक्षि वी[ठु] राच्छडपुत्रस्तथा वावण गौदासुतः ॥ लिखितं स्थानानुमतेन करणिकसर्व्वहरिणा
भीचुकपुत्रेणेति ॥ ❀ ॥ परमभट्टारकमहाराजाधिराजपरमेश्वरश्रीभोजदेवपादानुध्यातपरमभट्टारक-
महाराजाधिराज³⁵परमेश्वरश्रीमहेन्द्रपालदेवपादानां महीप्रवर्धमानकल्याण³⁶विजयराज्ये सम्बत्सरस -

5. तेषु नवसत [ष^x]द्यधिकेषु चतुरन्वितेषु मार्गसिरमासवहुलपक्षतृतीयायां सम्बत् ९६४
मार्गं वदि ३ अद्येह. सीयडोणिसमावासितमहाप्रातिहारसमधिगताशेषमहाशब्दमहासामन्ताधिपति-
श्रीउन्दभटः॥ समस्तराजपुरुषान्बोधयति विदितमस्तु भगवतां³⁷ अस्मिन् पत्तने नेमकवणिकचण्डुकप्रतिष्ठा-
पितविष्णुभट्टारकस्याम्माभि³⁸परलोकनिस्त्रेयसार्थं³⁹ पुण्ययसोभिहृद्ये यौवनधनजीवितानि नलिनीदलगतज-

6. ललवतरलतराणि लक्ष्य अक्षयनीमीयं निवेदिता ॥ सीयडोणिसत्कमण्डपिकायां प्रतिदिनं
पश्चियकद्रमसत्कपादमेकं दातव्यं तथा दिनं प्रति सुद्रयित्वा युगैका देया ॥ देवस्यावलेपनसम्मा³⁹र्जनाङ्गरागध-
पप्रदीपनैवेद्यार्थमाचन्द्रार्कक्षित्युदधिसमकालिनं यावत्पालनीयं कस्मिंश्चित्काले यः कोपि पुरुषः परिपन्यना-
ख्वा करोति उत्पादयति³⁹ स पञ्चमहापातकै लिप्यति स्वहस्तोयं श्रीउन्दभटस्य ॥ छ ॥

¹⁷ From impressions supplied to me by the Editor.

¹⁸ Expressed by a symbol.

¹⁹ Here about 8 *aksharas* are gone.

²⁰ Here about 96 *aksharas* are gone.

²¹ Here about 8 *aksharas* are gone.

²² Here about 12 *aksharas* are gone.

²³ I have little doubt that the preceding passage origin-ally was :— महराजपरमेश्वरश्रीभोजदेवपादानुध्यातपरमभट्टारकमहा-
राजाधिराजपरमेश्वरश्रीमहेन्द्रपालदेवपादानां ; as below, line 4.

²⁴ *I.e.*, 'विजयराज्ये संबत्सरशतेषु.—For the following नवसत
(*i.e.* नवशत, 900,) one would of course expect to read नवसु
'nine,' but the dates below are given in the same way. With
regard to षड्यधिकेषु, it is difficult to say whether the actual
reading of the stone, here and below, is षड्य० or षड्०.

²⁵ Here about 12 *aksharas* are gone.

²⁶ Here about 15 *aksharas* are gone.

²⁷ Here about 5 *aksharas* are gone.

²⁸ Here also about 5 *aksharas* are gone. The following
aksharas अ[कु?] are the remainder of पञ्चकलं.

²⁹ Here about 7 *aksharas* are gone.

³⁰ Here about 9 *aksharas* are gone.

³¹ Read बुद्ध्या.

³² This *akshara*, न, was originally omitted, and is en-
graved above the line.

³³ This word, which has no case-termination, qualifies the
following श्रीनारायणभट्टारकस्य.

³⁴ Read either श्रुते or श्रुतं.

³⁵ Originally महराज०.

³⁶ Read मकल्याण०.

³⁷ Read भवतां.

³⁸ Read मनिःत्रेयसार्थं.

³⁹ One of the two verbs is superfluous ; read स पञ्चमहापा-
तकैलिप्यति.

7. बहुलुद्रगणयोर्वारि . वारप्रमुखस्थानेन निवेदिता अक्षयनीमिका ॥ ❀ ॥ अक्षिनेव⁴⁰ काले तथा चण्डुकेन सङ्कटसुतेन प्रतिष्ठापितपश्चिमाभिमुखश्रीविष्णुभट्टारकस्य समर्पिता वणिकचण्डुकस्तथा सावसस्तथा माहपा⁴¹[दिभि?]स्वाङ्कटसुतैः स्वकीयस्वकीयच्छाया [आ]त्तीयप्रवासनिका उत्तराभिमुखा अस्याभ्यन्तरे उत्तराभिमुखगृहाणि चत्वारि अपसरकसहितानि अवलिप्तसिलाच्छ[त्रा]नि प्रवासनिकाया- [आ]घाटानि लिख्यन्ते [पूर्वे]ण र -

8. यथा दक्षिणेन चण्डुकीयावासनिकास्त्रोलिकापातं पश्चिमे⁴² सी⁴³कीयदेवसत्कप्रवासनिका उत्तरेण च्छेण्डिका मर्यादा एवं चतुराघाटचिह्नोपलक्षिता महद्भर्महेतोरवलेपनसम्भार्जनधूपप्रदीपनैवेद्यार्थं प्रदत्ता यः कश्चित्परिपत्यना करोति स च महानरकं व्रजति ॥ मतं चण्डुसावसमा⁴⁴हपानां साङ्कटसुतानामिति ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा सम्बत्सरसतेषु नवसत पञ्चषष्ट्यधिकेषु अक्षिनमासे प्रतिपदायां सम्बत् ९६५ अक्षि[न सु]दि १

9. वणिकनागाकेन चण्डुसुतेनापरिमितमूख्येन क्रीत्वा कुम्भकारदैवैकप्रदचागा[न्दू]कलिष्ठाकादीनां अक्षयनीमिका देवस्य समर्पिता ॥ छ ॥ तथा समस्तकक्षपालानां मध्ये यस्य यस्य सत्कमद्यभाण्डं नि०पद्यते विक्रयं याति स⁴⁵ च स चाचन्द्रार्कं यावद्विग्रहपालसत्कद्रुमार्चिका⁴⁶ ताली दातव्या ॥ यच्च⁴⁷श्चित्परिपत्यना करोति स नरकं व्रजति स्थानीयभूमौ ये भूये भूता⁴⁸ ये भविष्यन्ति कुम्भकारष्वलपालाश्च⁴⁹ तैरक्षयनीमिका पालनी -

10. या ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा वारप्रमुखस्थानसम्बद्धकन्दुकानां पार्श्वात् कन्दुक[ना]इलभोइलतिकूदेगू[प]-स[नू]कादीनां पार्श्वात् वणिकनागाकेन चाण्डुसुतेन सम्भार्जनविलेपनधूपप्रदीपनैवेद्यार्थं अपरिमितमूख्येन क्रीत्वा कन्दुकानां प्रतिवराहकयविंसोपकैकं प्रतिदिनं वि १ ग्राह्यमाचन्द्रार्कं यावद्भोक्तव्यं यच्चश्चित्परिपत्यनाखशामुत्पादयति स च महापातकपञ्चकैर्लिप्यति ॥ स्वहस्तोय ४४४४⁴⁸ मिति ❀ ॥

11. तथा सम्बत्सरसतेषु नव[स]त सप्त[ष^x]ष्ट्यधिकेषु फाल्गुनमास⁴⁰ अमावास्यां सम्बत् ९६७ फाल्गुन वदि १५ सीयडोण्यां वारप्रमुखस्थाने अश्वत्थानर⁵⁰सिंघयोर्वारि यथा नेमकवणिकचाण्डुकेन प्रतिष्ठापितश्रीविष्णुभट्टारकपश्चिमाभिमुखमुलाइतणदक्षिणदिग्विभागे नेमकवणिकवासुदेवेन प्रतिष्ठाप्य श्रीविष्णुभट्टारकं उत्तराभिमुखं महान्तधर्मार्थहेतोः पूजापनसम्भार्जनधूपप्रदीपार्थं

12. दोसिहृष्टे पूर्वाभिमुखावलिप्ताच्छत्रा उवटकसहिता देवस्य समर्पिता ॥ अस्याघाटानि लिख्यन्ते पूर्वेण हृष्टरथ्या⁵¹ दक्षिणेन वामनसत्कवीथी पश्चिमेन स्त्रोलिकार्पतमुत्तरेण⁵² श्रीविष्णुभट्टारकवीथी मर्यादा एवं चतुराघाटविशुद्धा प्रदत्ता ॥ तथा वैखान्दर⁵³पूजनार्थं वासुदे[वे^x]न स्वकीयगृहं पूर्वाभिमुखं उवटकसहितं प्रदत्तं अस्याघाटानि पूर्वेण प्रसन्नदेवियारकमर्यादा दक्षिणेन

13. वासुदेवगृहभित्ति०पश्चिमेन रथ्या उत्तरेण श्रीप्रसन्नवीथी मर्यादा एवं चतुराघाटविशुद्धं देवस्य प्रदत्तं यच्चश्चिह्नविधारणविधारणा⁵⁴ करोति स च नरकं व्रजति न संशयः⁵⁵ ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा वणिकचण्डु-

⁴⁰ Read अक्षिनेव. •

⁴¹ This *akshara*, पा, originally was प.

⁴² This *akshara*, मा, originally was म.

⁴³ One would expect तेन तेन.

⁴⁴ Read •द्रुमार्चिका.

⁴⁵ Read यच्चश्चि०.

⁴⁶ All these *aksharas* are quite clear in the impression, but I do not understand them.

⁴⁷ Read कुम्भकाराङ्कपालाश्च.

⁴⁸ These signs appear to have been put in to fill up the line. [Or they are meant for an actual representation of the sign-

manual; compare *Indian Antiquary*, vol. XIV, p. 198 f.—E. H.]

⁴⁹ One expects •मासे.

⁵⁰ This *akshara*, र, was originally omitted, and is engraved above the line.

⁵¹ Read हृष्टरथ्या.

⁵² Read स्त्रोलिकापातमुत्तरेण.

⁵³ I.e., वैखानर०.

⁵⁴ One विधारण appears superfluous.

⁵⁵ The *akshara* सं of this word was originally omitted, and is engraved above the line, before न.

कीयोपार्जना प्रसन्नहृदे उत्तराभिमुखा वीथी अवलिता उवटकसहिता अस्याश्चाघाटानि पूर्व्वेण सुभादित्यस⁶⁶
वीथी दक्षिणेन भृष्टदेवप्रसादसत्त्वावासनिकाखोलीपातं पश्चिमेन चूंभा -

14. वीथी उत्तरेण हृष्टरथा मर्यादा ॥ छ ॥ तथा अपरं चाण्डूकेन साङ्गुसुतेन पितृपितामहो-
पार्जितं स्वकीयं दक्षिणाभिमुखं वीथीचतुष्टयं अमीषामाघा[टा^x]नि⁶⁷ लिख्यन्ते पूर्व्वेण चूंभावीथी दक्षिणेन
हृष्टरथा पश्चिमेन स्वकीयावासनिकाद्दोषमर्यादा उत्तरेण स्वकीयावासनिका मर्यादा एवं चतुराघाटचिह्नो-
पलक्षिता⁶⁸ मातापितृोरात्मनश्च पुण्ययोभिहृष्टये⁶⁹ परमभक्त्या श्रीविष्णुभट्टारकस्य सा -

15. सनत्वे प्रदत्तं यद्दक्षित्परिपन्थनाखत्रा करोति स च महापञ्चपातकैः क्षिप्यति⁶⁰ नरकं व्रजति
॥ ❀ ॥ तथा [ग्र]हपतिकताम्बूलिककेशवेन वटेश्वरसुतेन पितृपितामहोपार्जितदक्षिणाभिमुखस्वकीयवीथी
चतुर्हृदे अस्याश्चाघाटानि लिख्यन्ते पूर्व्वेण कंसारकवीथी दक्षिणेन हृष्टरथा पश्चिमेन केशवस्य वीथी उत्तरेण
कंदासघूटमर्यादा एवं चतुराघाटविशुद्ध⁶¹ चण्डूप्रतिष्ठापितपश्चि[मा]भि -

16. [सु]खश्रीविष्णुभट्टारकस्य प्रदत्ता आचन्द्रार्कं यावत्पालनीया यद्दक्षित्परिपन्थना करोति स च
महापञ्चपातकैः क्षिप्यति⁶² ॥ वीथी इयं सांप्रतं पूर्वाभिमुखा वर्त्तते ॥ स्वहस्तोयं केशवस्य ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा नेमक-
वणिकनागाकेन चाण्डूसुतेन दोसिहृदे उपार्जनां कृत्वा वीथीद्वौ २ पूर्वाभिमुखी अवलिता⁶³ उवटकसहितौ
अनयोराघाटा लिख्यन्ते पूर्व्वेण हृष्टरथा दक्षिणेन वासुदेववीथी पश्चिमेन खोली[पा] -

17. [तं] उत्तरेण रामेवीथी मर्यादा एवं चतुराघाटचिह्नोपलक्षिता श्रीविष्णुभट्टा[र^x]कस्य
प्रदत्ता मातापितृोरात्मनश्च पुण्ययोभिहृष्टये यद्दक्षित्परिपन्थनावाधा करोति स च षष्ठीं वर्षसहस्राणि
षष्ठीं⁶⁴ वर्षसतानि च विष्टायां जायते कृमिः ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा नेमकवणिकसीलूकेन महापासुतेन उपर्जयित्वा⁶⁵
वीथी दक्षिणाभिमुखापसरकसहितावलिताच्छ्रमा⁶⁶ अस्याश्चाघाटानि लिख्यन्ते पूर्व्वेण सावसवीथी दक्षिणे-

18. न हृष्टरथा पश्चिमेन श्रीशिवभट्टारकवीथी मर्यादा एवं चतुराघाटविशुद्ध⁶⁷ श्रीनारायणभट्टा-
रकस्य धूपप्रदीपनैवेद्यार्थं प्रदत्ता यद्दक्षित्परिपन्थना करोति स च नरकं व्रजति महापञ्चपातकै-
क्षिप्यति⁶⁸ ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा सन्वत्सरनवसतेषु एकोनसप्तत्यधिकेषु माघमासे पञ्चम्यां⁶⁹ सन्वत् ९६९ माघ शुदि
५ अद्येह श्रीमत्कीयडोण्यां महाराजाधिराजश्रीधू[र्भ]ट⁷⁰परिभुज्यमाने⁷⁰ . तत्पादाधिष्ठितलोधुआकादि-
पञ्चकुलं

19. मण्डपिकायां कौस्तिकरस्थाकः स्थानारोपितअबुआनरसिंघयोर्व्वारे सतीदृसे काले वर्त्तमानं
[ने]मकवणिकनागाकेन चाण्डूसुतेन समस्तकल्लपालानां पार्श्वात् अपरिमितमूल्येन क्रीत्वा कल्लपालमहत्तक-
पश्चिकः सांतडस्तथा राहडस्तथा कुण्डाकस्तथा ललाकस्तथा जसकरकादीनां समस्तकल्लपालानां सत्कहृष्टा-
नामुपरि दत्तश्रीमदादी⁷¹[वरा]हपञ्चासदधिकानि सतानि त्रयोदशाङ्के वराहद्र १३५० अ -

20. तीर्थे सुराभाण्डं प्रति मासाभ्यासं विग्रहत्तुङ्गीयद्रमार्द्धं दातव्यं तालिं प्रति वि १० आचन्द्रा-
र्कक्षितिकालिनं धूपप्रदीपनैवेद्यार्थं श्रीविष्णुभट्टारकस्य प्रदत्तं यद्दक्षिणविधारणा करोति स च नरकं
व्रजति ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा नेमकवणिकनागाकेन चाण्डूसुतेन मातंगानां पार्श्वाद्दुपार्जित⁷² मह[द्व]र्णार्थहेतो⁷³
दोसिहृदे युगेकं युगेकं प्रति कपर्दकद्वयं द्वयं क२ दातव्यं मातङ्गकीवेजोहृटाकस्तथा देरुलाकस्तथा रउंभाक-

⁶⁶ Probably for सुभादित्यस्य or सुभादित्यसत्क.

⁶⁷ One would expect अमीषामाघाटानि or आसामाघाटानि.

⁶⁸ One would expect here •क्षिप्यति or below प्रदत्ता.

⁶⁹ Read •हृष्टये.

⁷⁰ Read •क्षिप्यति.

⁷¹ One would expect •विशुद्धा.

⁷² Read •क्षिप्यति.

⁷³ One would expect अवलिता, and below •क्षिप्यति, and
प्रदत्ता.

⁷⁴ Read षष्ठीं वर्षसहस्राणि षष्ठीं.

⁶⁵ Read उपार्जयित्वा, for उपार्ज.

⁶⁶ Originally •लितासच्छ्रमा.

⁶⁷ One would expect •विशुद्धा.

⁶⁸ Read •क्षिप्यति.

⁶⁹ One would expect शुक्लपञ्चम्यां.

⁷⁰ Read •टपरि०. Before, one would expect •कीयडोषि-
पत्तने (as in lines 29, 30, and 36), to agree with परिभुज्यमाने.

⁷¹ Read श्रीमदादि०.

⁷² One would expect •पार्जित.

⁷³ Read •हेतीर्हीसि०.

21. स्तथा संकराकस्तथा⁷⁴ येस्वराकस्तथा हेम्ब[टा]कादीनां⁷⁵ दोसिहृटे समस्तयुगानामुपरि अक्षय-
नीमिका प्रदत्ता यङ्कोपि परिपत्यना करोति स च नरकं व्रजति ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा नागाकेन दोसिहृटे
उपार्जिता⁷⁶ पूर्वाभिमुखा वीथी अवलिप्ता उवटकसहितास्याश्वाघाटानि पूर्व्वेण हृटरथा दक्षिणेन भट्टजेहरि-
वीथी पश्चिमेन खोलीपातं उत्तरेण च्छेडिका मर्यादा एवं चतुराघाटविशुद्धा श्रीनारायणभट्टारकस्य स -

22. सर्पिता यङ्कोपि परिपत्यना करोति स च नरकं व्रजति ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा नागाकेन
चाण्डूसुतेनात्मीयदक्षिणाभिमुखवीथीत्रयं उवटकसहितं अमीषां⁷⁷ अघाटानि लिख्यन्ते पूर्व्वेण शिवभट्टार-
कवीथी दक्षिणेन हृटरथा पश्चिमेन श्रीमाकीयदेववीथी उत्तरेण नागासत्कभवामनिकाखोलीपातं एवं
चतुराघाटचिह्नोपलक्षिता विलेपनसम्भार्जनधूपप्रदीपनैवेद्यार्थं श्रीनारायणभट्टारकस्य समर्पिता

23. यङ्क्षित्परिपत्यना⁷⁷ करोति स च न[र^x]कं व्रजति ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा स्थानानुमतेन
वारपपद्मयोर्व्वारं नमकवणिकभाइलेन गोविन्दसुतेन श्रीवामनस्वामिदेवपश्चिमाभिमुखस्य पितृपितामहो-
पार्जित⁷⁸ उत्तराभिमुखा वीथी अवलिप्ता उवटकसहिता अस्याश्वाघाटानि लिख्यन्ते⁷⁹ पूर्व्वेण सीगासत्कदेव-
वीथी दक्षिणेन खोलीपातं पश्चिमेन पुन⁸⁰ सीगासत्कदेववीथी उत्तरेण हृटरथा मर्यादा एवं चतुराघाट-
चिह्नोप-

24. लक्षिता धूपप्रदीपनैवेद्यार्थं प्रदत्ताचन्द्रार्ककालिनं यावत् रसीके विग्रहपालीयद्रुमभृत्तृभागं⁸¹ तृ १
देवस्य दातव्यं यङ्कोपि परिपत्यना करोति स च नरकं व्रजति ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा नागाकीयउपार्जना पूर्वा-
भिमुखी गृहद्वी अवलिप्तौ अपसरकसहितौ अस्याश्वाघाटानि⁸² पूर्व्वेणाकासभोगप्राङ्गणं दक्षिणेन
वामनगृहभीती पश्चिमेन खोलीपातं उत्तरेण च्छेडिका मर्यादा एवं चतुराघाट -

25. चिह्नोपलक्षिता सम्भार्जनविलेपनगन्धधूपप्रदीपार्थं प्रदत्तं तृभुवनस्वामिदेवस्य⁸³ यङ्क्षित्प-
रिपत्यना करोति स च नरकं व्रजति ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा नागाकीयउपार्जनायां उत्तराभिमुख⁸⁴ उवटकं ब्रा[ह्म]ण-
ताम्बोलिकधमाकेन क्रयित्वा महन्तधर्मार्थहेतो⁸⁵ श्रीउमामहेश्वरस्य प्रदत्तं अस्याघाटानि पूर्व्वेण शिवभट्टारक-
वीथी दक्षिणेन खगृहभित्ति⁸⁶ पश्चिमेन शिवभट्टारकवीथी उ -

26. उत्तरेण हृटरथा मर्यादा एवं चतुराघाटविशुद्धं य७परिपत्यना करोति स नरकं व्रजति ॥ ❀ ॥
सम्बत् ९९४ वैशाख वदि ५ सक्रांती⁸⁷ चण्डूकीयदेवस्य इह निवासी ताम्बोलिकमहर सवर केसवासुतस्तथा
भाधव इच्छसुत⁸⁸ समस्तलोकानां मिलित्वा अक्षयनीमिका प्रदत्ता पण्णपालिकां प्रति विग्रहद्रुमविसोवकं
विसोवकं प्रदत्तं वि १ आचन्द्रार्ककालिनं भोक्तव्यमिति⁸⁹ ॥ स्वहस्तं सवरमाधवयोः ॥ ❀ ॥

27. [त]था सावसकीय दक्षिणाभिमुखा वीथी अवलिप्ता⁹⁰ उवटकसहिता कृतोपसन्ना अस्याघा-
टानि⁹¹ पूर्व्वेण सीगाकीयदेववीथी दक्षिणेन हृटरथा पश्चिमेन सीलूवीथी⁹² उत्तरेण खोलीपातं एवं चतुराघाट-
विशुद्धं विलेपनसम्भार्जनधूपप्रदीपनैवेद्यार्थं तृभुवन⁹³स्वामिदेवस्य प्रदत्ता यङ्कोपि परिपत्यना करोति स
महापातकपञ्चकै⁹⁴ लिप्यति ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा नागाकीयउपार्जना⁹⁵ तैलिकवीठु तथा नारायणस्तथा ना-

⁷⁴ Originally •कादिनां.

⁷⁵ Originally उपार्जित.

⁷⁶ One expects अमीषां or आसां.

⁷⁷ Originally •पत्याना; read •क्षित्परिपत्यना.

⁷⁸ One expects •पार्जिता.

⁷⁹ Read लिख्यन्ते.

⁸⁰ Read पुनः.

⁸¹ Read •त्रभागं वि.

⁸² One would expect here अनयीयाघाटानि, and below

•लक्षिता and प्रदत्तौ.

⁸³ Read तृभुवन०.

⁸⁴ One expects •मुखं.

⁸⁵ Read •हेतोः.

⁸⁶ Read •भित्तिः.

⁸⁷ Read सक्रांती.

⁸⁸ One expects the Instrumental case, here and before.

⁸⁹ Read भोक्तव्यमिति.

⁹⁰ Read अवलिप्ता.

⁹¹ One would expect here अस्या अघाटानि, and below
•विशुद्धा.

⁹² This akshara, घी, was originally omitted, and is en-
graved above the line.

⁹³ Read तृभुवन०.

⁹⁴ Read •कैलिप्यति.

⁹⁵ Read उपार्जना.

28. गदेवस्तथा महसोणः समस्ततैलिकानां घ्राणकं घ्राणकं प्रतिदिनं⁹⁶ महान्तधर्मार्थहेतोः तैलपलिका प्रदत्ता ॥ ❀ ॥ परमभट्टारकमहाराजाधिराजपरमेस्वरश्रीचित्तिपालदेवपादानुध्यात⁹⁷रम-भट्टार[क^x]महाराजाधिराजपरमेस्वरश्रीदेवपालपादानां महीप्रवर्धमानकल्याणविजयराज्ये सम्बत्सराणां सप्तमेकं पञ्चोत्तरं माघमासशुक्लपक्षपञ्चम्यां सम्बत् १००५ माघ शुदि ५ अद्येह

29. श्रीमत्सीयडोणपत्तने 'महाराजाधिराजश्रीनिष्कल⁹⁸रु⁹⁹रिभुज्य[मा^x]ने मण्डपिकायां सीयपादिपञ्चकुलं स्थानानुमतेन 'पा¹देदेकयोर्वारे सतीदृसे काले वर्त्तमाने दोसिहटे समस्तमहा-जनेन एकमतीभूत्वा महान्तधर्मार्थहेतोर्वणिकविक्रमेन⁹⁹ प्रतिष्ठापितश्रीभाद्रलखामिदेवस्य प्रदत्तं मासान्वासं प्रति द्रम्यस्य तृभागं¹⁰⁰ तृ १ देयमिति ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा सूत्रधारजेजपस्तथा विसिष्ठाकस्तथा भलुष्ठाकस्तथा जो[गू]-

30. [क]द्रकादीनां समस्तघाहाडसम्बत्सिलाकूटानां¹ एकमतीभूत्वा श्रीविष्णुभट्टारकस्य भरणं भरणं प्रति विषयपालद्रम्यस्य तृभागं² तृ १ अचन्द्राककालिनं यावन्नोक्तव्यं यक्कश्चित्परिपत्यना करोति स च महापातकपञ्चकौर्षिप्यति ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा सम्बत् १००८ माघ शुदि ११ अद्येह सीयडोणपत्तने महाराजा-धिराजश्रीनिष्कल⁹⁸स्तत्पादाधिष्ठितपुरंदरादिपञ्चकुलं मण्डपिकायां³ कौत्तिकमाधवः स्थानाधिष्ठिततुण्डि-प्रद्युम्नयोर्वारे

31. इहाधिष्ठाने चण्डुप्रतिष्ठापितश्रीविष्णुभट्टारकायतने पुरन्दरेण प्रतिष्ठापितपश्चिमाभिमुख-श्रीचक्रलखामिदेवस्य दीपतैलार्थं इह निवासी तैलिकानां केसवस्तथा दुर्गादित्यस्तथा के[सु]लाक उजोणेक तुण्डिष्ठाकादीनां³ महान्तधर्मार्थहेतो⁴ घ्राणकघ्राणकं प्रति तैलपलिका प्रदत्ता यक्कश्चित्परिपत्यना करोति स च नरकं व्रजति ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा पूर्वसूचित नेमकवणिकपप्पाकेन देदडासुतेन यत्प्रतिष्ठापित श्री[च] -

32. क्रस्वामिदेव[स्य] वणिकमहादित्यनोहलाभ्यां पप्पासुताभ्यां [चात्मीया]वासनिका उत्तरा-भिमुखास्याभ्यन्तरे उत्तराभिमुखानि⁵ गृहाणि त्रीणि ३ अपसरकप्राङ्गणसहितावलिप्तानि अस्याघाटानि⁶ पूर्व्वेण रथा दक्षिणेन खोलीपातं पश्चिमेन चाण्डूसत्कावासनिका उत्तरेण हारोष्ठनिष्कासप्र[वे]सक मर्यादा एवं चतुराघाटचिह्नोपलक्षिता विलेपनसम्भार्जनधूपप्रदीपनैवेद्यार्थं प्रदत्तं यक्कश्चित्परिपत्यना करोति स च नरकं [व्र] -

33. जति ॥ स्वहस्तोयं महादित्यनोहलयोः ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा पूर्व्वसूचित स[म्बत्] ९९१ माघ शुदि १० नगाकः⁷ वाण्डूसुतस्तथा [दे^x]दैकस्तथा वालिस्तथा रुदाक जाजूसुतास्तथा च्छित्तराकः सावासुत एकम-तीभूत्वा स्वकीयस्वकीयच्छाया महान्तधर्मार्थहेतो⁸पूर्व्वीभिमुखा अवासनिका अपसरकप्राङ्गणसहिता अस्या-घाटानि⁶ पूर्व्वेण निष्कासप्रवेसहारोष्ठकं दक्षिणेन विषयणकङ्कपसत्कावासनिका पश्चिमेन कविलासत्क[अवा]-

34. सनिका उत्तरेण सावससत्कअवासनिका मर्यादा एवं चतुरा[घा]टविशुद्धा अस्याभ्यन्तरे समस्तगृहसमेतां समस्तवीथीसमेतां च देवस्य प्रदत्ता यक्कोपि वि[घ्नं?] करोति स चात्मीयपुरुषचयं नरकं नयति यक्कोपि वीथीषु प्रवसति स च गोष्ठिभावितं भाटकं ददाति दायादस्या[धि]कारं नास्ति स्वहस्तोयं नागादेदेवालीरुदाकादीनां मतं लिखितं सर्व्वह[रि^x]पुत्रेण रच्छाकेन ॥ ❀ ॥ तथा देदैकस्तथा वालीकस्त[था]

⁹⁶ In my opinion, one would expect either प्रति प्रतिदिनं, or only प्रति ; see below, line 31.

⁹⁷ Read⁹⁷ ०ध्यातपरम०.

⁹⁸ Read ०लक्षपरि०.

⁹⁹ Read विक्रमेण.

¹⁰⁰ Read त्रिभागं त्रि.

¹ One would expect here the Instrumental case.

² Read त्रिभागं त्रि १ अद्य०.

³ Here again I should have expected the Instrumental (or दत्त).

⁴ Read ०हेतीर्षा०.

⁵ Originally उत्तरीभि०.

⁶ Comparing line 7 above, one would expect here अवास-निकायाघाटानि, and below प्रदत्ता.

⁷ Read नागाकः चाण्डू०.

⁸ One would expect here अस्याघाटानि, and below अस्या-भ्यन्तरे समस्तगृहसमेता समस्तवीथीसमेता च.

⁹ The akshara in brackets looks rather like वधं, or वध

35. तथा¹⁰ रुदाक जाजूसुतारेभि¹¹ प्र[दत्ता] चण्डुप्रतिष्ठापितपश्चिमाभिमुखश्रीविष्णुभट्टारकस्य चतुष्कहटे¹² पश्चिमाभिमुखा वीथी अवलिप्ता उवटकसहिता कृतोपसन्ना अस्याघाटानि लिख्यन्ते¹³ पूर्वेषु [श्री]लीपातं दक्षिणेन श्रीअ[म्ब]लीहीदेविजगति¹⁴पश्चिमेन हृदरथ्या उत्तरेण तिखरावीथी मर्यादा¹⁴ एवं चतुराघाटविमुखा विलेपनसम्पन्न¹⁵धूपप्रदीपनैवेद्यार्थं प्रदत्ता [यङ्ग] -

36. श्वित्परिपन्थना करोति स च नरकं घोरं व्रजति पितृपितामहैस्सह ॥ स्वहस्तोयं देदेवाली- रुदाकादीनां सम्पत्तं लिखितं स्वामिकुमारेण सर्व्वहरिसुतेनेति ॥ ❀ ॥ सम्बत् १०२५ माघ वदि ९ अद्येह सीयडोणिपत्तने महाराजाधिराजश्रीनिष्कलङ्कपरिभुज्यमाने तत्पादाधिष्ठितकेशवराजादिपञ्चकुलं स्थानानुमतेन पाङ्कदेदेकयोर्व्वारि सतीदृसे काले इहाधिष्ठाने द -

37. [क्षि]ण दिग्विभागे चाण्डुप्रतिष्ठापितपश्चिमाभिमुखश्रीविष्णुभट्टारकस्वायतने नेमकजाति- वणिकमहादित्येन पेपेसुतेन प्रतिष्ठापिनपूर्वाभिमुखश्रीविष्णुभट्टारकस्य वणिकश्रीधरेण महादित्यसुतेन विले- पनसम्पन्नपूजापनधूपप्रदीपनैवेद्यार्थं श्रीमदादी¹⁶वराहद्रमस्य पादैकं प्रदत्तं एतदर्थं मासाभासं प्रति दीयमानं पञ्चियकद्रमैकं सास -

38. [नं] लिखितं अङ्के पं द्र १ एतदर्थं [सा] च वीथी [नागासत्का] दक्षिणाभिमुखा उवटकसहिता कृतोपसन्ना भोगाधिना तिष्ठति अस्याघाटानि¹⁷ लिख्यन्ते पूर्वेषु श्रीशिवभट्टारकवीथी दक्षिणेन हृदरथ्या पश्चिमेन सोल्लुक्वीथी उत्तरेण श्रीलीपातं मर्यादा एवं चतुराघाटविमुखा अस्या वीथ्या मोचापनकाले अपरवीथी अनुरूपा¹⁸ सासने लिखाप्य मोक्तव्या आचन्द्रार्क -

39. क्षितिकालिनं यावद्गो[क्तव्यं] यङ्गक्षि[त्खश्रावाधा?][ददाति] स च महान्तं नरकं व्रजति मतं सिरिधर महादित्यसुतस्य लिखितं करणिकधीरवर्मणा¹⁹ स्वामिकुमारसुतेनेति ॥ ❀ ॥ श्री²⁰ श्री नमो, गणपतये । घ्रंतु²¹ वो गणनाथस्य हस्ताक्षेपवमंथवः । विघ्नं रेणुं क्षितेः क्षिप्रं विन्दुभिर्जलदा इव ॥ योसौ²² [च]- क्राम धात्रीं गिरिकुहरसरित्सागरानूपरम्यां पादेनैकेन कृत्स्नां वलिच्छलनव -²³

40. [शा^x]भूर्ति[मास्या]य [ङ्ग]खां । स्वर्ग[म्ब्राम?]²⁴ साकं पवनप[ङ्ग]गणैर्भा[नुचन्द्र]ग्रहाप्यैः सोव्यान्निविक्रमो व[स्तु]²⁵तयपदपथो यस्य देवैर्ब लब्धः²⁶ ॥ महोदयामरावत्यां²⁷ मनुष्येन्द्रेण धीमता । रायकं नाम नगरं ब्राह्मणेभ्यो²⁸ ददे²⁹किल ॥ रायकभट्टा इति ते ख्यातिं प्राप्ता महीतले । दातारः शत्रुजेतारो विद्वांसो सुवहृश्रुताः²⁹ ॥ तेषां³⁰ प्र -

41. तीतकुलसंततिसुप्रसूतिश्चारित्र[चा]रधनधैर्ययुतो व[शि]ष्ठः । शिष्टप्रहर्षजनकः स कली [वभूव]³¹ सद्भावभावरिभावितचित्तवृत्तिः ॥ ³²शुभ्रास्ततु[ल्यैर्भ]वनैर्व्विरा[जि]तात्कैलासमृङ्गादिव गुह्यका- धिपः । द्रव्यहृही[त्वा] किल मातृयानकात्केनापि कार्येण चरन्निहागतः ॥ ³³तेना[क्षि]न्नगरीन्द्रकंदरमुखे दृष्टो नृपः शिंहव³⁴[च्छी]मद्राजकुले[भ] -

¹⁰ This is wrongly repeated here.

¹¹ Read रुदाकी जाजूसुता एभिः.

¹² Read ०हटे.

¹³ Read (अस्या अघाटानि) लिख्यन्ते.

¹⁴ Read मर्यादा.

¹⁵ Read ०सम्पन्नं.

¹⁶ Read श्रीमदादि०.

¹⁷ One would expect अस्या अघाटानि.

¹⁸ Read अनुरूपा.

¹⁹ Originally ०वर्मणा.

²⁰ Expressed by a symbol.

²¹ Metre, Śloka (Anuṣṭubh).

²² Metre, Sragdharā.

²³ Read वलि०; the second syllable of this word is used as a short syllable, notwithstanding the following च्; and

in the following line य is used as a short syllable before the conjunct ङ्.

²⁴ Read स्वर्ग [वभाम?].

²⁵ Read वलि०.

²⁶ Read लब्धः.

²⁷ Metre, Śloka (Anuṣṭubh); and of the next verse.—

Originally ०मरावरावत्यां.

²⁸ Read ब्राह्म०.

²⁹ Read सुवहृ०.

³⁰ Metre, Vasantatilakā.

³¹ Read वभूव.

³² Metre, Indravamśā.

³³ Metre, Śārdūlavikrīḍita.

³⁴ Read शिंह०.

42. दृष्यमनप्रो[द्]तगुंजारवः । मत्वा कौतुकपूरितान्तरगतो* रात्रः समीपेवस[च्छी]मन्त
हरिराजमाहवह[रे]रासाथ पूजामनु ॥ तस्यात्मजः³⁵ स्यात्तगुणोपपन्नो दामोदरो नाम [ज]गत्प्रसिद्धः
सोसारतां वीक्ष्य हिरण्यजीवात्कारापयामास गृहं सुरारिः ॥ आवाणपुंजैरिव सिद्धकोस्त्रिन्सोपानमाह्वय
ग[तोन्त] -

43. रिक्तम् । शृङ्गं हिमाद्रेरिव वनरेण [आ?]नीय [सु]क्तं [ल?]वणाध्विवंधात्³⁶ ॥ ये[नाभू]विजवाहु-³⁷
पंजरहृद्गुह्याहना रोदसी दृसप्रोद्गतदैत्यैकटुकठिनच्छेदोद्दम[च्छो]णितैः । क्वातां [य]स्य वसुंधरा करवरैर्द्वीता
पवित्रीकृता तस्यार्चां प्रविवेस³⁸ लक्षणवतीं त्रैविक्रमीयां शुभाम् ॥ ³⁹मोरानीपार्जुनांमैर्गगनप[रि]चि -

44. तैस्तालमालामधुकै[र्वा]रथा राजजंघा⁴⁰ फलभरनमितैर्हाडि[मीमातुलंगैः] । [जातीने?]-
वालजालैर्विकसितसुमनोमल्लिकामंजरीभिः पुष्पै[र्व]न्यप्रधानैः सम[श?]नरुचिरै राजितं* वृक्षपण्डैः ॥
प[त्तनात्पूर्वमारामं]⁴¹ मंदाकि[न्या] दिगुत्तर[म्] ।] ददौ स नित्यपू[जार्थ]न्तस्मै सत्कारसिद्धये ॥ विप्रकीय-
गृहपश्चिमभा[गा?] -⁴²

45. हेवभूमिनिल[यात्पु]रतश्च । दक्षिणेन वणिजी⁴³ निजरथ्य उ[त्तरे]ण उ उ - उ उ [पश्चात्] ॥
[त]स्य⁴⁴प्रतिमासं - - - [लो]हवानाम् । दोष - - [मं]डपिकायामध्वर्ष[का]किणीं
- [दिने दिने] ॥⁴⁵[हारिकां प्रति] वराटकै[कां] १ - - - देव्याः - - -
णर[था]⁴⁶कगृहं १ वसन्तमह[त्त]कहृष्टे [व] -

46. णि[ग]⁴⁷ महत्तकहृष्टे⁴⁸पुर[तो] र[था] च्छि⁴⁹ ॥ -
[जा]⁵⁰ पूरि उ उ - [रयशः]पताका - - उ - [रणमुखे त्रि]दिवं प्रयातः । [तस्या]त्मजेन
वरविप्रनतांश्रियुग्मो दामोदरेण उ उ - उ उ - उ - - ॥ ❀ ॥

XXII.—A STONE INSCRIPTION FROM KUDARKOT (GAVIDHUMAT).

BY PROFESSOR F. KIELHORN, PH.D., C.I.E.; GÖTTINGEN.

The stone which bears this inscription is said to have been found, in 1875, in the ruins of the Fort of Kudârkot, in the Itâwâ District of the North-Western Provinces, 24 miles north-east of Itâwâ town; and it is now in the Lucknow Museum.

The inscription contains 16 lines. The writing covers a space of about 2' 4" broad by 1' 4" high, and is well preserved almost throughout. The size of the letters is between $\frac{1}{8}$ " and $\frac{5}{8}$ ". The characters belong to the northern class of alphabets, and they are in every respect very similar to those of the Bodh-Gayâ inscription of Mahânâman of the (Gupta) year 269, = A.D. 588-89, a photo-lithograph of which has been published in the *Indian Antiquary*, vol. XV, p. 358. As regards individual letters, it may be noted that *r*, as the first part of a conjunct, while it is ten times denoted by the superscript

³⁵ Metre, Indravajrâ, and of the next verse.

³⁶ Read •ध्विवन्धात्.

³⁷ Metre, Śārdūlavikrīḍita; read •बाहुपंजरहृद्•.

³⁸ Read प्रविवेस, used for the Causal.

³⁹ Metre, Sragdharâ; read •नामै•.

⁴⁰ Read •जम्भा.

⁴¹ Metre, Śloka (Anushtubh).

⁴² Metre, Svâgnâtâ; the last *akshara*, गा, appears to be engraved above the line.

⁴³ Originally वणिजी णिजी, but the second णिजी is struck out.

⁴⁴ Here about 10 *aksharas* are illegible in the impression.

⁴⁵ Here about 11 *aksharas* are illegible.

⁴⁶ Here about 6 *aksharas* are illegible.

⁴⁷ Here about 8 *aksharas* are more or less illegible.

⁴⁸ Here about 13 *aksharas* are illegible.

⁴⁹ Here about 11 *aksharas* are illegible.

⁵⁰ Metre, Vasuntatilakâ.

ARCHÆOLOGICAL SURVEY OF INDIA.

EPIGRAPHIA INDICA:

A COLLECTION OF INSCRIPTIONS
SUPPLEMENTARY TO

THE CORPUS INSCRIPTIONUM INDICARUM

OF THE
ARCHÆOLOGICAL SURVEY,

TRANSLATED BY SEVERAL ORIENTAL SCHOLARS.

EDITED BY

JAS. BURGESS, LL.D.; C.I.E.,

HON. A.B.I.B.A., F.R.G.S., M.B.A.S.; M. SOC. AS. PARIS.

HON. OF MEM. BRIT. SOC. OF ANTHROPOLOGY, ETC., AND OF BATAVIAN SOC. OF ARTS AND SCIENCES, FELLOW OF THE UNIVERSITY OF BOMBAY, ETC.
LATE DIRECTOR-GENERAL OF THE ARCHÆOLOGICAL SURVEY OF INDIA.

ASSISTANT EDITORS.

E. HULTZSCH, PH.D.,

EPIGRAPHIST TO THE GOVERNMENT OF MADRAS

A. FUHRER, PH.D.,

ARCHÆOLOGICAL SURVEYOR, NORTH-WESTERN PROVINCES AND OUDH.

VOLUME I.

CALCUTTA:

PRINTED AND PUBLISHED BY THE SUPERINTENDENT OF GOVERNMENT PRINTING, INDIA.

CALCUTTA—THACKER, SPINK & Co. BOMBAY—THACKER & Co., LD.

LONDON—KEGAN PAUL, TRENCH, TRUBNER & Co., BERNARD QUARITCH, LUZAC & Co.

PARIS—E. LEROUX. LEIPZIG—OTTO HARRASSOWITZ.

1892.

All rights reserved.